

GENERAL CONCEPT OF IJMA

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Annotation: Muslim law is one of the major legal systems in the world (along with continental Anglo-Saxon legal systems). It came to the Arab Caliphate in the 7th-10th centuries. Criticism of Muslim law is based on the requirements of Islam, the morality of Muslims, and the punishments for which they are violated (ordinary, religious). The Qur'an, Sunnah, consensus, comparison, and tradition are the main sources of Muslim law. In this article, opinions and comments on the concept of consensus are discussed.

Keywords: Ijma, law, Muslim, Qur'an, rule, Islam, morality.

Muslim law applies only to relations between Muslims. However, despite the strong position of Muslim law in Asia and Africa, where Muslims make up the majority of the population, it has been supplemented by laws and customs that take into account new social relations. It is therefore necessary to distinguish between religious Muslim law and the law of Muslim states. In 1869-77, al-Majalla, which had served as a civil code in the Ottoman Empire, was proclaimed on the basis of codification of the obligatory and procedural norms of Muslim law. Muslim law was in force in Turkey until 1926, in Lebanon in 1932, in Syria in 1949, and in Iraq until 1951. The effect of this code is partially preserved in Jordan, Israel and Cyprus. Beginning in the second half of the 19th century, Muslim countries adopted criminal, commercial, procedural, and other codes based on the use of Western European law. It plays an important role in the regulation of Muslim rights, family, heritage and other relations. The codification of these branches of Muslim law is carried out in the form of the adoption of special laws in MAP, Syria, Iraq, Jordan, Tunisia, Morocco, India, Pakistan and other countries. In some Arab countries, such as India, Pakistan, Indonesia, and elsewhere, the influence of Muslim law codified on the personal status of Muslims (as well as on non-Muslims in some respects) has been preserved. The constitutions of a number of Arab countries allow Muslim law to be the basis of legislation and to apply it in civil law and other areas; Shariah compliant courts have been maintained in these countries. In some countries in East and Central Africa, Muslim law is applied as a common law.

Sharia (Arabic: right path; used in Islam in the sense of legislation) is an Islamic legal system. In addition to purely legal issues, the Shari'ah also provides for moral norms and practical religious requirements. The Shari'ah is seen as a set

of rules that govern a Muslim's behavior from birth to death. In early Islam, the legal management of society was based on the Qur'an. Later, there was a need for a set of laws covering all socio-economic, political, legal and religious activities of Muslims. Islamic jurists have been developing Shari'ah norms for centuries. The Shari'ah is based on the Qur'an, the Sunnah, consensus and comparison. Sharia as a legal system was fully formed in 11-12. It was influenced by written and oral religious, cultural, moral, legal, and local customs and traditions.

In Islam, there are certain differences between Sunni and Shiite systems of Sharia. Sunnis have their own legal systems of Hanafi, Maliki, Shafi'i, Hanbali, and Shiite Jafari. The Shari'ah contains the rules of state (caliphate) law, obligations, inheritance, criminal, criminal, and family law, as well as judicial and guardianship instructions. The Shari'ah considers private property to be God-given, permanent, and unchanging. In the Shari'ah, all actions are initially divided into two types - haram and halal. Later, when the Shari'ah was formed and completed, it was divided into five categories. These are: fard or wajib - actions that are important and obligatory (prayer, giving zakat); sunnat or mustahab - norms that are not obligatory, but are acceptable and necessary (marriage, giving alms); permissible or permissible - voluntary actions that are not encouraged and non-compliance is not considered a sin (agreement, trade, travel, food, drink, etc.); makruh - actions that are not punishable, but are considered unacceptable (swearing, disrespect for adults, water pollution, overloading animals); unclean and strictly forbidden acts (eating pork, drinking vodka, murder, etc.). It provides for strict, brutal measures for this crime.

In short, The Shari'ah sciences cover Islam and related issues. These include tajweed, tafsir, hadith's, jurisprudence, jurisprudential parts of jurisprudence, and theology. The Shari'ah sciences also include Arabic language and literature, as it is considered impossible to study the Shari'ah sciences without them.

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